

GREENING ROOFS IN UZBEKISTAN - THE NEED FOR ECOLOGICAL HEALTH, CONVENIENCE AND BEAUTY

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Abstract: In this article is highlighted the information about the authors propose to use gardens on the roofs which come to us from time immemorial, today they become one of pressing needs of a society in its aspiration to ecologically pure environment.

Key words: uncomfortable negative emotions, ultraviolet radiation, biointerior, megacities, green bioinclusions.

Architecture, in accordance with the laws of convenience and beauty, plays a large role in the formation of the material living environment in which people live, work and relax. The problem of the connection between nature and climate with architecture today is becoming even more important, when the most perfect accounting of microclimatic influences on humans becomes one of the important tasks in the design, reconstruction and improvement of buildings and structures. Given this relationship, greening roofs is a pressing issue, because living plants on city roofs are an excellent symbol of the ecological improvement of the urban environment, but unfortunately, they are not yet sufficiently and timidly accepted by architects and builders. Huge areas of roofs of industrial, residential and public buildings, underground structures constitute an irreplaceable reserve of urban areas. They can be used in different ways - for parking lots, for placing utility units, or engineering devices on them. But, at the same time, they can be a kind of artificial foundation for gardens, squares and other objects of landscape architecture. On the one hand, landscape inclusions play an aesthetic role in urban planning, and on the other hand, they protect the roof structures of buildings and structures from damage. Plants, by absorbing moisture, protect roofs from destruction and reduce the load of wastewater.

Plants in the city that serve as “lungs” will acquire additional helpers, because modern buildings, overheating, emit heat and harmful volatile substances, which typically worsen the climate in the city. These impacts can be reduced by greening roofs. German scientists have found that green roofs can reduce air temperature by three times, and in our hot climate this is very important. Despite the reduction in air temperature, aesthetics and protection of roofs, plants on roofs have other positive aspects. They help reduce dust by holding dust on the surface of the leaves. Even a small lawn retains up to 50% of dust in the passing air flow, and with watering the percentage increases. In our hot climate, we should not forget about ultraviolet radiation, which is also reduced when plants are planted on the roof. In summer, plants on roofs help to reduce background noise due to foliage, but in winter this effect does not work.

Those areas that are located along highways, or near the airport area, i.e. where there is much more noise, planting plants on the roof is necessary. Plants purify the air of microbes,

absorbing carbon dioxide and dust, saturating the air with oxygen, which is why we need them so much in the life of megalopolises, cities and regions. We must also appreciate the effectiveness of green roofs. It remains to evaluate and determine to what extent a garden, square, or rooftop lawn meets the needs of people, their psychology, habits, and lifestyle. Currently, we are more striving for environmentally friendly housing, namely, we build houses from natural materials, finishing them with modern environmentally friendly materials, which is why we so need the presence of plants in our bio-interiors. In our interiors, plants can be used in the form of winter gardens on balconies and loggias, and used on the facades of buildings. And if we combine plants inside the house, with plants next to the house and plants on the roof, then, in our opinion, we get the ideal home of the future, which people are increasingly striving for.

Environmental benefits of greening roofs: **A** - due to greening, the temperature of the roof surface and air is reduced; **B** - plants absorb dust and toxic emissions; **C** - plants reduce noise by having a sound-absorbing effect; **D** - plants partially absorb rainfall, thereby protecting roofs. Today's city dwellers, living in apartment buildings, especially on the upper floors, working in offices that lack green bio-inclusions, are largely deprived of those wonderful contemplations of living nature. A feeling of being "disconnected" from the ground can be felt in such premises, and if an apartment or office is located on floors higher than previous buildings, then people also feel a certain visual discomfort that arises when viewing the unaesthetic roofs of urban buildings. What cannot be said about the green spaces of roofs, to some extent roofs - gardens, which with their landscaping and their aesthetic beauty can relieve uncomfortable negative emotions? The improvement of roofs and their landscaping can be directed towards a cultural and educational regime, namely, using roof gardening for relaxation, short walks, communication, even for playing some sports, raising children, and accustoming them to a wonderful aesthetic moment, and this, in its turn, will enrich our modern and fast-paced life with new content. On a properly prepared surface, you can create an attractive corner of the garden. General view of the "Spanish" garden "Derry and Toms" on a multi-story building in London an example of a roof garden in a private apartment on one of the terraces of a skyscraper in New-York.

Short rest between work and work among plants will definitely improve both health and efficiency. Architecture will be the more progressive and the more fully it meets the requirements of creating a full-fledged material living environment of society, satisfying practical and aesthetic needs, the more fully and widely people use the benefits of nature, armed with the latest scientific, technical and artistic achievements of their time, using not only natural landscapes on earth, but also on the roofs.

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